

ESA DATA DISCOVERY PORTAL

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ABSTRACT

Over several decades, ESA has been producing a wealth of data holdings coming from its spacecrafts. This data treasure is preserved and made available to the world-wide scientific community through science data archives, usually organized by discipline (i.e. Space Science, Earth Science, Human and Robotic Exploration), and distributed through different dissemination systems and web sites with distinct types of interfaces (web GUI, scriptable API, visualization tools, ...).

While each of these archives and dissemination systems is designed to serve their respective communities and meet specific user and scientific requirements, there is a need for a unified portal, where all ESA data holdings can be referenced through a common ontology. This portal should allow for queries through simple searches, as well as provide access to the corresponding data archive and access system for visualization, download or further analysis through the science platforms made available by ESA (e.g. ESA Datalabs).

This is the purpose of the ESA Data Discovery Portal, located at data.esa.int, under which all ESA data holdings have been given a dedicated Digital Object Identifier (DOI), that will also ensure a permanent identifier for all data holdings in the long term, even if the underlying mission data archive entry point might change over time.

Science data archives at ESA

Through its various programmes, ESA is producing a wealth of datasets under an open and free data policy that can be accessed from different dissemination systems or websites to support their specific communities, in particular:

- Space Science missions through ESAC Science Data Centre – <https://archives.esac.esa.int/>
- Earth Observation missions through Earth online portal - <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway>
- Earth Observation Copernicus missions through its Open Access Hub - <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>

- Human and Robotic Exploration through its Data Archive - <https://hreda.esac.esa.int/>
- ESA GNSS Science Support Centre through its portal - <https://gssc.esa.int/>

All these archives offer user-oriented services, through web searches portal (GUI) and scriptable interfaces (API), tuned to the scientific community they are serving. The underlying software systems represent complete data management systems as described in the Open Archiving Information System (see OAIS at [RD-01]), from storage, database, validation, ingestion, querying, dissemination, and overall archive administration and preservation planning aspects.

To respond to users and scientific needs, each archive needs to implement specific data services (i.e. data model, querying mechanisms, data visualization, ...), which depend on the type of datasets the archive provides. For example, searching for a region on Earth is very different from searching for a particular object in the universe, or again for the strength of a solar eruption from the Sun. Visualizing images of a comet as observed by Rosetta is very different from displaying the evolution of a biology or microgravity experiment on board the International Space Station (ISS).

Defining a DOI for every ESA dataset

From a preservation perspective, there is a common need to define a persistent and unique identifier for each of these datasets. This ensures the long-term availability and accessibility of these datasets. It also contributes to the implementation of the FAIR data principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable ([RD-02]). A DOI is a persistent and unique resource identifier pointing to a landing page that provides a description and a download link for the particular dataset. At ESA, the minting of DOIs were initially performed through the CrossRef Registration Agency and through DataCite since January 2023.

The first step of this activity was to define a common set of metadata to describe all ESA datasets, which mainly includes:

- Dataset name
- Mission name and description
- Instrument
- Scientific domain
- Dataset Description
- Dataset version
- Publishing date
- Temporal coverage
- Link to the actual data
- Publisher and associated information
- Credit and citation Guidelines

All this information is displayed as part of the DOI landing page, as shown in **Figure 1**.

A dataset provided by the European Space Agency

Name	SWAN, Solar Wind Anisotropies
Mission	SOHO
URL	https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/soho/soho-science-archive
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5270/esa-45tj9pn
Abstract	On board the SOHO spacecraft, positioned at L1 Lagrange point, the SWAN instrument is mainly devoted to the measurement of large scale structures of the solar wind, and in particular the distribution with heliographic latitude of the solar wind macro flux. This is obtained from an intensity map of the sky Lyman alpha emission, which reflects the shape of the ionization cavity carved in the flow of interstellar H atoms by the solar wind. The instrument is composed of one electronic cell containing two identical Sensor Cells, each of them allowing to ring a full hemisphere with a resolution of 1° thanks to a two-mirrors perspective system. A hydrogen absorption cell is used to measure the shape of the interplanetary Lyman alpha line and other Lyman alpha emissions.
Description	Daily sky maps in Lyman alpha provided as FITS files
Publication	Berkaev, J.I., et al., SWAN. A study of Solar Wind Anisotropies on SOHO with Lyman alpha sky mapping. Sol. Phys. 162, 403-430 (1995). https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00733435
Temporal Coverage	1996 - April 2017
Mission Description	SOHO, the Solar & Heliospheric Observatory, is a project of international collaboration between ESA and NASA to study the Sun from its deep core to the outer corona and the solar wind. SOHO was launched on December 2, 1996. The SOHO spacecraft was built in Europe by an industry team led by prime contractor Alcatel Marconi Space (now Airbus) under overall management by ESA. The science instruments on board SOHO were provided by European and American scientists. None of the international instrument consortia was led by European Principal Investigators (PIs) hired by ESA from the start. Large engineering teams and more than 200 co-investigators from many institutions supported the PIs in the development of the instruments and in the preparation of their operations and data analysis. NASA was responsible for the launch and is now responsible for mission operations. Large radio dishes around the world which form NASA's Deep Space Network are used for data downlink and commanding. Mission control is based at Goddard Space Flight Center in Maryland.
Creator Contact	Domingo, V., Fleck, B. & Poland, A.I., The SOHO mission: An overview. Sol. Phys. 162, 1-37, 1995. https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00733425
Publisher And Registrant	European Space Agency
Credit Guidelines	When publishing any works related to this experiment, please cite the DOI found herein.

Figure 1: Example of DOI landing page for the SOHO mission

Determining granularity level for DOI assignment

Specific attention had to be paid to the level of granularity at which to define a DOI. We realized that there can be great variety depending on the type of datasets produced by a particular mission.

For astronomy survey missions, the datasets are usually in the form of a catalogue of astronomical objects (e.g. Gaia) or cosmology maps (for Planck). In that respect, only a few DOIs will be minted for these missions. For astronomy observatory missions (i.e. HST, XMM – Newton or Herschel), astronomers submit proposals for a scientific topic that, once accepted, will result in various observations distributed over time. In this case the DOIs are minted at proposal level and can still represent several thousand DOIs for each of these missions. In the Planetary science domain, the granularity is defined at “planetary dataset” level, which

corresponds to data and documentation collected by an instrument for a particular phase of a mission (typically a few months long) and for a particular version of this dataset. Overall, it results in a few thousand DOIs for all ESA planetary missions. For heliophysics missions, the level of granularity is defined at the experiment level over the course of the entire mission lifetime. Therefore, only a few tens of DOIs are needed for all ESA heliophysics missions.

Overall, around 30.000 DOIs have been minted so far for the ESA Space Science Missions as shown in **Figure 2**, and the number will keep increasing to cover new observations and new missions.

Science Mission	Domain	DOIs
HST	Astronomy	10901
XMM - Newton	Astronomy	4270
ISO	Astronomy	3877
Rosetta	Planetary	3594
Mars Express	Planetary	3512
CHEOPS	Astronomy	2971
Herschel	Astronomy	741
Venus Express	Planetary	727
SMART-1	Planetary	22
SOHO	Heliophysics	13
Cluster	Heliophysics	12
Ulysses	Heliophysics	12
Giotto	Planetary	10
ExoMars TGO	Planetary	10
Planck	Astronomy	9
Cassini-Huygens	Planetary	8
Lisa Pathfinder	Astronomy	8
Double Star	Heliophysics	8
Solar Orbiter	Heliophysics	7
Chandrayaan-1	Planetary	6
Proba-2	Heliophysics	5
Gaia	Astronomy	4
ISS-SolACES	Heliophysics	1

Figure 2: DOIs per ESA Space Science Missions

For Earth Science, the level of granularity has been defined in line with the guidelines and best practices defined in the frame of the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) [RD-06]. As a general rule, DOIs are assigned to data collections (e.g. a consistent time-series) rather than to individual data products or scenes. The resolved DOIs should then lead to the original Landing Page of the Data Collection in which the final user can retrieve any relevant provenance information and consequently the proof of the data integrity and authenticity. In addition, the Landing Page provides a link to access the data itself. In case of complete data collection reprocessing, e.g., to exploit new algorithms for quality improvement, a new DOI is assigned to the new data

collection. Several hundred DOIs have been assigned to Earth Observation Data Collections managed at the ESA Earth Observation Centre (ESRIN).

For Navigation, the diverse range of data holdings available at the GSSC datalake are organized into 'Collections' and 'Datasets'. At high level, 'Collections' represent an entity associated to data holdings generated by a project, experiment, mission or coordinated group such as networks of Continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS). At a lower level, 'Collections' are further decomposed into "Datasets", allowing for the creation of groups of data holdings that share specific characteristics within the "Collection" such as different reprocessing versions. In the case of Navigation, DOIs will be minted at "Dataset" granularity leading to the generation of approximately thirty DOIs. Currently (March 2023), DOIs for the Navigation Data Archive are being produced, with the first DOI planned to be minted for the GREAT dataset in Q2.

At the time of writing this paper (March 2023), DOIs for the Human and Robotic Exploration Data Archive are still to be produced, but these are expected to be assigned at experiment dataset level (a few thousand references).

ESA Data Discovery Portal

Once DOIs were minted for all ESA datasets with a common set of metadata, it became much easier to produce a unified portal from which all ESA datasets could be referenced. The ESA Data Discovery Portal was created and made accessible at <https://data.esa.int/>. It is important to understand that this portal is not a data archive per se, and therefore does not supersede the existing archives and associated data dissemination services built for each mission within the ESA directorates. ESA Data Discovery Portal complements existing archives by aggregating information to provide a unique entry door to all ESA datasets (each of them gets a unique reference in the form of <https://data.esa.int/asset/<reference>>) and then providing the link to the corresponding datasets.

Figure 3: ESA Data Discovery Portal

The ESA Data Discovery Portal offers very simple search fields (see Figure 3), "Google-like", and quickly returns the corresponding results of datasets. Through the faceted search options on the left, users can fine tune their search along various parameters such as scientific domain, thematic area, missions, instrument as well as type of assets (datasets or analysis/visualization tools called "datalab").

By clicking on one of the datasets, all associated metadata are displayed, providing details of such data holdings and links to the corresponding data archive where the data holding resides and can be downloaded as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Example of a Planck dataset description in ESA Data Discovery Portal

Relationship with Google Dataset Search

In January 2020, Google released a new search engine, called Google Dataset Search, helping users to find various types of datasets published online. Google Dataset Search relies heavily on dataset providers to make their own data easy to search by their engine. This can be achieved by adding validated structured metadata, based on the schema.org vocabularies. Since ESA datasets can in principle be

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